

Enhancing the realism of decarbonisation scenarios with practicable regional constraints on CO₂ storage capacity

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ABSTRACT

Most low-carbon scenarios produced by integrated assessment models deploy substantial amounts of carbon capture and storage (CCS). These models generally assume that CO₂ storage is a low-cost and globally ubiquitous resource. Here we challenge this assumption, introducing a CO₂ storage potential which accounts for the financial, contractual, and institutional barriers to CO₂ storage, which we term the investable potential. We provide a first estimate of this investable potential and utilise a global energy system model to explore the implications for global and regional mitigation pathways. Our results suggest that low-carbon scenarios which assume abundant CO₂ storage may substantially overestimate the role of CCS in deep decarbonisation, particularly in key regions such as China and India. Limited CO₂ storage leads to mitigation pathways with faster emission reductions and greater reliance on renewable energy for decarbonisation. We demonstrate that the optimal use of CCS depends heavily on the availability of CO₂ storage, with different use-cases prioritised at different scales of storage availability. Finally, we present exploratory analysis on the potential for cross-border trade in captured CO₂ to match sources and sinks. The results of this analysis can help calibrate expectations and inform policy decisions around the role of CCS in addressing climate change.

1. Introduction

Deep decarbonisation pathways which meet the Paris Agreement goals tend to rely on substantial amounts of carbon capture and storage (CCS) (Clarke et al., 2014; Riahi et al., 2022; Rogelj et al., 2018). Such pathways are the result of scenarios built using integrated assessment models (IAMs) and are influential tools informing climate policy design through, for example, the reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). In IAM scenarios which limit warming to 1.5°C in the SR1.5 database (Byers et al., 2022), median CCS deployment reaches 7.5GtCO₂/y by 2050 and over the century around 700GtCO₂ is captured and sequestered (Fig. 1). CCS is a valuable mitigation option in these scenarios due to its perceived versatility. IAMs deploy CCS in a wide range of situations to reduce emissions, including providing firm low-carbon power (Koelbl et al., 2014), industrial decarbonisation (Psarras et al., 2017), low-carbon hydrogen production (Voldund et al., 2016), and generating negative emissions via engineered removals (Daggash et al., 2019). However, real-world deployment of CCS continues to fall short of expectations (IEA, 2020; Reiner, 2016; Wang et al., 2021), with deployment still lagging almost all trajectories produced by

IAMs Peters et al. (2017).

Most IAMs and energy system models producing low-carbon scenarios assume that CO₂ storage capacity (mainly in deep saline aquifer formations) is globally ubiquitous and low-cost. The majority of IAMs use CO₂ storage potential estimates in excess of 3000GtCO₂ (Table 1). This perspective is underpinned by estimates of subsurface storage capacity which indicate there is enough pore space to contain the required amount of CO₂ (Dooley, 2013; Dooley et al., 2005; Hendriks et al., 2004; Kearns et al., 2017). Although true on a purely volumetric basis, static volumetric estimates do not consider the myriad of technical and non-technical factors which limit practicable injection rates, simply providing an upper limit of storage potential that would be accessible were there no constraints on the rate of CO₂ injection. In reality, as well as permanently containing injected CO₂, commercial CCS projects require reservoir CO₂ injection rates to match CO₂ capture rates from source facilities. This must occur for the lifetime of projects, and at an acceptable cost per tonne of CO₂. When considering “rate-matched” or dynamic capacity requirements, static volumetric indicators are not instructive, because permeability rather than porosity dominates (Lane et al., 2021).

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Fig. 1. Displays CCS deployment in scenarios which limit end-of-century warming to 1.5°C from the AR6 database (Byers et al., 2022).

Here, we explore the sources of discrepancy between the scale of CCS deployment in modelled scenarios and its real-world potential. Following Lane et al. (2021), we argue that conventional IAM scenarios may be overestimating the potential for CCS by relying on static volumetric estimates of storage potential. Using an energy system model, we explore the implications of limited CO₂ storage potential for low-carbon scenarios.

1.1. The central importance of CO₂ injection rates

It has long been recognized that dynamic constraints on injection rates will limit the ultimate, practicable storage capacity that can be achieved in geologic formations. Frailey (2009) discusses this concept, using a mathematical model to highlight that injection rates can decline over time as the pressure builds in a reservoir. The reality of injectivity constraints, and potential solutions to overcome these constraints, has been further explored in recent work (Agada et al., 2017; Bachu, 2015; Garnett, 2019; Garnett et al., 2019; Thibeau and Mucha, 2011). Declining injection rates could result in the need to vent CO₂; and/or a requirement for additional injection wells or engineered pressure management responses (both with associated additional cost); and/or increasing injection pressures beyond safe design conditions. To alleviate such risks prior to investing, partners in CCS projects will require a high level of confidence in the dynamic capacity of the storage formation, i.e. the sustainable injection rate over the life of the project. However, aside from locations with a history of oil and gas (O&G) exploration and production, much of the CO₂ storage potential relied upon by IAMs has not been characterised sufficiently to support such confidence.

Lane et al. (2021) underscore how CO₂ storage capacity uncertainty threatens both the pace and scale of CCS expansion, especially in high emitting countries with limited O&G industry experience (e.g., India and China). In areas without pre-existing subsurface activity (such as oil and gas extraction), data inadequacies create uncertainty around the feasible injection rates into a given reservoir. This then contributes to the cross-sectoral risk that CCS projects face, as the financial viability of any potential CO₂ source is dependent on the continued performance of the sink, which is uncertain. If the sink is unable to sustain injection rates, source operators must vent CO₂ or reduce their capacity, both of which will result in financial loss and contractual dispute. While a range of solutions to the injectivity challenge have been proposed, their ability to

Table 1
Representation of CO₂ storage in Integrated Assessment Models.
Table displays CO₂ storage potentials, and assumptions on injection rates, for six well-known and influential IAMs. For further detail on CCS representation in these models, plus a comparison with TIAM-Grantham see Supplementary Table 1.

Variable	REMIND	GCAM	WITCH	AIM/CGE	IMAGE	MESSAGE
Storage potential	Global storage potential of around 3700GtCO ₂ is assumed and regional constraints are also placed.	Global storage potential of 7178 GtCO ₂ is assumed	Default global storage potential of 11000GtCO ₂ is assumed.	No explicit constraint on the storage potential is applied, but ex-ante comparison is performed with global storage potential estimates to ensure consistency.	Global storage potential of 5500GtCO ₂ is assumed.	No explicit constraint on the storage potential is applied.
Injection rate	The yearly injection rate of CO ₂ is limited to 0.5% of total storage capacity due to technical and geological constraints. This corresponds to a maximum injection rate of 21.9GtCO ₂ /y.	Injection rate constraints are not modelled.	Injection rate constraints are not modelled.	Injection rate constraints are not modelled.	Injection rate constraints are not modelled.	Injection rate constraints are not modelled.
Source	(Bauer, 2005; Luderer et al., 2015)	(Bond-Lamberty et al., 2021; Mahasenan et al., 2005)	(Chen and Tavoni, 2013; Realmonde et al., 2019)	(Fujimori et al., 2017)	(Hendriks et al. 2004; IAMC-Documentation, 2021)	(Fricko et al., 2017; Huppmann et al., 2019; Krey et al., 2020)

entirely overcome injection rate decline is uncertain (Lane et al., 2021). A more effective way to improve confidence in long-term injection rate dynamics is by detailed characterisation of the storage resource, using extended well tests and field development engineering (Harding et al., 2018; Mackay, 2013). This, however, requires large-scale, up-front, and at-risk investments in exploration, appraisal, field development planning and permitting of storage reserves. It also requires the institutional and industrial expertise to carry out subsurface characterisation, injection pattern design and associated pipeline sizing – expertise which is strongly correlated with historical O&G extraction (Herzog, 2017).

This creates a set of contractual (cross-sectoral risk), financial (significant at-risk pre-investment capital required to reduce uncertainty in feasible injection rates) and institutional (need for critical expertise from both industry and the regulator) barriers to successful CCS deployment in the next two to three decades. The risk is that, in locations with limited O&G industry experience, these barriers combine to subdue investment confidence in the viability of CCS projects (Fig. 2).

Notwithstanding these challenges, numerous individual source-to-sink proposals have successfully appraised sufficient storage capacity to support large-scale, integrated CCS project investments (e.g., Equinor's Sleipner and Chevron's Gorgon projects). These projects highlight again the importance of addressing uncertainty in CO₂ injection rates, the high costs and use of critical expertise in doing so, and the role of historical O&G extraction as a key enabling factor in successful CCS deployment to-date. For example, Chevron spent \$200m on exploration, appraisal and field development planning on the CO₂ storage formation before successfully taking the final investment decision on the Gorgon project (Harrington, 2014). On the other hand, illustrating the at-risk nature of such characterisation costs, the ZeroGen project spent over \$100m on storage exploration and appraisal, before determining that the project was not viable as the reservoir could not competitively sustain the required injection rates (Garnett et al., 2012). In addition, notable multi-source CCS proposals (e.g. the UK's Teesside and Humber net-zero hubs) are also poised to proceed to final investment decisions (FID) later this decade (Mace, 2021; Mavrokefalidis, 2020). These rely on multi-operator contracts which deal with counterparty risk. However, all of these projects are predominantly found in areas where there is a significant existing oil and gas (O&G) industry (Herzog, 2017), with associated knowledge of subsurface resources and available institutional capacity on behalf of both sink operator and regulator. Even in this favourable context, establishing confidence in injection rates and project feasibility, negotiating and settling multi-party contracts, regulatory permits and investment approvals continue to take a decade or more.

Despite the central importance of CO₂ injection rates in determining practicable storage capacity, very few IAMs explicitly constrain CO₂ injection rates (Table 1). Here, we argue for the need to urgently establish a global atlas of *investable* CO₂ storage capacity – comprising granular, regionally resolved, dynamic storage capacity estimates based on sustainable injection rates; and that static volumetric estimates of CO₂ storage capacity are misleading when assessing the potential scale of CCS deployment. In the absence of such an atlas, we provide an *ad hoc* indicator of this potential (after Lane et al., 2021) and implement it in a global energy system model to assess its implications for emissions and energy system configurations at both global and regional levels. We explore what low-carbon transitions might look like when subject to investable CCS potentials, by applying regional constraints to CCS deployment in line with regional O&G production capacity. To explore uncertainties, we conduct sensitivity analyses around discount rates, the level of the investable potential and the potential for cross-border trade of CO₂.

2. Material and methods

2.1. TIAM-Grantham

The energy system model used in this analysis is TIAM-Grantham, a

version of ETSAP-TIAM (Loulou, 2008; Loulou and Labriet, 2008) maintained by the Grantham Institute. TIAM-Grantham is a bottom-up technology-rich model (Krey, 2014; Pfenninger et al., 2014; Weyant, 2017; Wiese et al., 2018), which considers the full energy chain from extraction of energy resources, via conversion technologies, to the provision of energy service demands to end-users. TIAM-Grantham is a least-cost optimisation model, calculating the energy system transition which will meet future energy service demands at minimum cost, subject to user-defined constraints such as cumulative carbon budgets and resource availability. The model assumes partial equilibrium within energy markets, allowing demand to respond endogenously to changes in energy prices. In this analysis, the model is run with perfect foresight. TIAM-Grantham disaggregates the world into 15 different regions, which are interlinked by the trade of the main energy commodities, material commodities such as cement, and (in this analysis) sequestered CO₂.

TIAM-Grantham represents over 30 different CCS technologies across a range of energy system sectors, including fuel supply (both bioliquids and hydrogen), electricity generation (bioenergy-CCS and fossil-CCS), energy intensive industries (including cement, steel, chemicals, paper and pulp), and carbon dioxide removal via bioenergy with CCS (BECCS) and direct air capture (DACCS). This detailed representation of CCS is essential to exploring the impact of CO₂ storage constraints in low-carbon scenarios. Recent literature was surveyed to ensure that the costs of CCS in TIAM-Grantham are accurately represented. For further details, see Supplementary Tables 1–3.

2.2. Estimating the investable potential for CO₂ storage

2.2.1. Existing estimates of CO₂ storage potential

Previous work has categorised estimates of storage capacity and placed them into a “techno-economic resource pyramid” with theoretical potential at the bottom of the pyramid, a technical potential in the middle that is subject to technical limitations, and a viable potential at the very top which applies economic, legal and regulatory barriers to the lower levels (Bradshaw et al., 2007). Other analysis considers a “practical potential” by further constraining the technical potential from existing assessments by excluding portions of offshore sedimentary formations (via water depth and shore distance) and excluding latitudes above 66° north and south (the Arctic and Antarctic regions); arriving at an estimate of practical global storage of 8,000 GtCO₂ or enough for about 200 years of storage at current emissions levels (Kearns et al., 2017). Finally, a “matched” potential of 290 GtCO₂ that attempts to geographically “match the best and nearest storage sites to large emission sources” has been reported (Dooley, 2013). However, the applied definition of matching is based on linking total project-life volumes of emissions to available sinks within geographic proximity and does not consider injection rate matching.

Some assessments (Dooley et al., 2005; Kearns et al., 2017) do account for injection rate constraints but do so via a “capacity coefficient” on the technical potential for CO₂ storage which is globally extrapolated from estimates based on U.S. data (Kearns et al., 2017). The US, however, is not representative of the rest of the world in more ways than one. First, US injection rate limitations will likely differ from what may be found in other regions (IOGP, 2019; Jahediesfanjani et al., 2018). Second, the US has a long history of subsurface characterisation and exploration with strong institutions and a mature regulatory environment. Third, the US financial system is uniquely placed to enable investment into risky projects as exemplified by its unconventional oil and gas resource extraction market which remains unduplicated anywhere else in the world (Bocora, 2012; Le, 2018).

Recent industry efforts have begun to catalogue storage resources, with the aim of providing investors a level of confidence in the availability of storage capacity (OGCI and Pale Blue Dot, 2020). This is a welcome development which could improve low-carbon scenarios by providing a more realistic estimate of CO₂ storage capacity. However, as

Fig. 2. Summarises how uncertainty in CO₂ injection rates into geological storage, and the contractual, financial and institutional barriers that this creates, could mean that CO₂ storage is a scarce resource that is concentrated in regions which can overcome these barriers.

a repository for the current state of knowledge around storage potential, rather than an active effort to map storage potential, there remains large gaps in the data provided by these efforts. Where data is available, it highlights the substantial difference between estimates of CO₂ storage from static volumetric methods, and potential estimates based on discovered resources, which largely correlate with historical O&G extraction. For example, while the theoretical storage capacity in China from submitted data is 3000GtCO₂, only 11GtCO₂ of this has been discovered, all of which is in O&G fields. This much smaller potential would still need to undergo detailed exploration, appraisal and field development planning before reaching final investment decision, which would be contingent on achieving suitable and sustainable injection rates into these reservoirs. The practicably accessible potential in China is therefore likely much smaller than 11GtCO₂ at the present time. While such a CO₂ storage potential could potentially support some demonstration projects, scaling up CO₂ sequestration to support a multi-GtCO₂/y scale industry, as envisaged in IAM scenarios, would require exploring, appraising and developing a much larger storage portfolio. Here the contractual, financial and institutional barriers to developing investable confidence in CO₂ sequestration rates would continue to pose substantial feasibility challenges, particularly if this scale up needs to be achieved by mid-century.

2.2.2. Investable CO₂ storage potential

Estimating the investable potential for CO₂ requires reliable data on feasible injection rates at a high enough resolution to account for regional variations and local conditions (Michael et al., 2011). In

addition, it should consider the institutional capacity required to develop a sequestration industry capable of delivering commercial projects at required scales and timing. Such a global storage appraisal atlas would be a valuable dataset in designing low-carbon scenarios produced by IAMs. However, it does not yet exist at a comprehensive level and global scale, especially in developing countries and emerging markets. Given the importance of CCS in low-carbon scenarios, such an estimate is invaluable to inform climate policy at global and regional levels. In the absence of such a database, we propose a simple *ad hoc* representation of this data that can be easily implemented in models in a transparent manner. This allows us to explore the implications for energy system models of the more constrained investable potential for CCS. The rationale for our *ad hoc* representation is given as follows.

First, we note that detailed characterisation of candidate geologic formations is essential to accurately estimate long-term injection rates and is thus critical to the investment case for any integrated CCS project. Such characterisation is expensive and requires specific knowledge and capabilities that only the O&G sector has. These costs of characterisation also remain fully at risk until the final investment decision is made on the integrated project. Hence, absent substantial public support, characterisation costs can present a critical barrier to development of individual projects and/or large-scale expansion of CCS deployment. Regions with historical O&G production already have well-characterised subsurface resources however, reducing this barrier.

Secondly, lack of core skills and expertise (both technical and regulatory) in regions without substantial O&G exploration and production make it challenging to start such characterisation reliably, and the large

scale of a global CCS industry would put these core skills in high demand.

We therefore suggest that historical oil and gas production might be a potential indicator of investable potential for CO₂ geologic sequestration in a given region. More specifically, we propose that the maximum historical rate of O&G production is one indicator of available knowledge of subsurface resources and of institutional/regulatory capacity, both essential components of any successful CCS endeavour and any region's ability to support a gigaton-scale CCS industry. Thus, it can serve as an initial indicator of the realistic sequestration potential in each region, in the absence of more detailed databases on investable CO₂ storage potential. There are certain locations where CO₂ storage is occurring absent historical O&G extraction, such as DACCS pilots in Iceland (Sankaran, 2021). While this highlights the potential limits of historical O&G extraction as a proxy for the investable potential, it should be noted that this example is a pilot project sequestering 4000tCO₂/year and is not an indicator of large-scale CO₂ storage potential. The majority of successful CCS projects to-date have been in O&G producing regions (Herzog, 2017), demonstrating that this proxy is likely still a useful indicator¹.

We use this indicator to provide a first estimate of the investable CO₂ storage potential, constraining CO₂ storage to be less than the historical maximum level of O&G extraction in a given region, in Mt/y. We use available national O&G production data (BP, 2019) and aggregate it to TIAM-Grantham regions, taking the maximum historical value. This results in a global limit on CO₂ sequestration of 8.6 GtCO₂/y, which we assume can be reached by 2050 (i.e., sequestration can reach the scale of maximum historical O&G extraction in each region within the next thirty years). The regional breakdown is provided in Table 2, alongside static volumetric estimates of CO₂ storage capacity used in

Table 2

Maximum historical oil and gas production aggregated to TIAM-Grantham regions and the assumed default volumetric storage capacity in TIAM-Grantham. Note that the historical extraction rates are annual and in Gt of oil and gas extracted per year while the TIAM storage capacity is total available storage in GtCO₂.

Region	Maximum historical O&G extraction (Gt oil/gas extracted per year)	Volumetric estimate of CO ₂ storage capacity (GtCO ₂) in TIAM-Grantham
Africa	0.80	1029
Australasia	0.13	538
Canada	0.39	702
China	0.33	518
Central and South America	0.64	1039
Eastern Europe	0.12	256
Former Soviet Union	1.41	1231
India	0.08	508
Japan	0.004	5
Middle East	2.17	789
Mexico	0.23	271
Developing Asia	0.43	1071
South Korea	0	10
USA	1.27	1128
Western Europe	0.59	300
Global Potential	8.6 Gt/y	9390 GtCO₂

¹ The location of CCS facilities in O&G producing regions is also likely governed by the availability of an additional revenue stream via enhanced oil recovery (EOR). In the absence of specific and targeted support for CCS, EOR revenues could continue to be a key enabler of CCS projects, which would further exacerbate the link between historical O&G production and future CO₂ storage potential.

TIAM-Grantham (Hendriks et al., 2004), which represent the technical potential for CO₂ storage assumed in the analysis.

The investable potential is a dynamic constraint, and it is thus not appropriate to compare directly to static volumetric estimates of CO₂ storage capacity currently represented in TIAM-Grantham. Table 2 does suggest however that, despite the large volumes of CO₂ storage capacity available, only one thousandth of this volumetric potential could be utilised per year when considering various limits to injection rates, and thus even over a century, at most ~10% of this potential could be accessed. Although already a much lower estimate of CO₂ storage potential, this may still prove optimistic depending on how soon storage is required, as it means scaling up the CO₂ sequestration industry in just a few decades to levels that took the O&G sector more than 100 years to accomplish.

2.3. Scenario description

We produce 1.5°C-compatible scenarios with variations in the CO₂ storage potential and the possibility of cross-border trade in captured CO₂. We first explore how moving from a technical to an investable estimate of CO₂ storage potential affects mitigation pathways at a global and regional level. We then produce scenarios which systematically explore CO₂ storage potential, assessing how mitigation pathways change as possible CO₂ injection rates vary between 0 and 30GtCO₂/y. Finally, we enable interregional trade in captured CO₂ to explore the possible role of a global market in captured CO₂. We conduct sensitivities around the discount rate used, the investable storage potential assumed, and the cost of trading in captured CO₂.

The technical potential for CO₂ storage is given by static volumetric estimates of CO₂ storage capacity commonly applied by IAMs (Hendriks et al., 2004). When modelling the investable potential for CO₂ storage, we build on this reference case by implementing the regional values shown in Table 2 (left column) as upper limits to the amount of CO₂ that can be sequestered on an annual basis in each region. In our central analysis, this injection rate can be achieved by 2050, representing a 30-year scale-up period for the CCS industry.

Our analysis of the potential for trade in sequestered CO₂ is exploratory in nature, and as such we represent these trade flows at a high level. Trade is allowed between all regions, with a shipping cost of \$28/tCO₂ (USD₂₀₁₀). This represents an average shipping distance of 6000km, in a ship carrying 50ktCO₂ at 10Mpa (IEAGHG, 2004), and is in line with surveyed literature (Element Energy, 2018; Kler et al., 2016; Roussanaly et al., 2013; ZEP, 2011).

All scenarios use SSP2 socio-economic drivers (Dellink et al., 2017; Oliver Fricko et al., 2017), and include a limit on sustainable biomass of 100EJ/y in 2050, growing to 130EJ/y by 2100. This represents a biomass potential for which there is large agreement in the literature (Creutzig et al., 2015). A 2018-2100 carbon budget of 580 GtCO₂ is applied, consistent with limiting end-of-century warming to 1.5°C with a 50% likelihood (Rogelj et al., 2018) (Supplementary Note 2).

3. Results

3.1. Impact of regional constraints on the global pathway

Fig. 3 summarises the consequences of moving from the technical to the investable CO₂ storage potential. With storage capacity given by the technical potential, global CCS deployment reaches 5 GtCO₂/y by 2050 and grows to 25 GtCO₂/y by the end of the century (Fig. 3a). Pre-2050, CCS deployment at the global scale is not significantly affected by the application of investable CO₂ storage estimates, but the potential for large-scale expansion in the latter-half of the century is substantially reduced. It takes until 2090 to reach the maximum 8.6GtCO₂/y, as there are regions with excess storage capacity but low domestic demand for CCS, which don't fully utilise their capacity until late in the century when carbon dioxide removal (CDR) via DACCS (a truly global good)

Fig. 3. The impact of limits to CO₂ injection rates. The figure demonstrates how regionally constrained CCS deployment affects the energy transition via a range of indicators. Panels show (a–d): Global CCS deployment, CO₂ emissions, carbon prices and mitigation investments. For comparison, the interquartile range and 90% confidence interval from 1.5°C scenarios in the AR6 database are shown in blue (selecting only SSP2-based scenarios). (e–g): change in final energy, electricity generation and fossil fuel consumption.

can be deployed at scale. This is particularly true for the Middle East, which has the largest investable potential for CO₂ storage. Cumulative sequestration across the century falls from 850GtCO₂ to 420GtCO₂ when moving from storage estimates based on the technical to the investable potential.

Because CCS is a critical component of CDR via BECCS and DACCS (the two CDR methods included in TIAM-Grantham), limited CO₂ storage reduces CDR deployment. The potential for net-negative emissions in the latter half of the century is curtailed, and there must be greater near-term emission reductions (Fig. 3b). Emissions fall 47% in the next decade in scenarios when the investable potential constrains CCS deployment (compared to 33% with technical potential), and reach net-zero in the mid-2050s, a decade earlier than otherwise. The need for faster decarbonisation with limited CCS leads to higher policy costs. The

marginal abatement cost more than doubles when investment-based constraints on CO₂ storage are applied (Fig. 3c), and the extent of mitigation investments necessary by the mid-century increases by approximately 50% and remains higher across the time-period (Fig. 3d).

If CO₂ storage resources are scarce, the role of CCS in facilitating deep decarbonisation is reduced, with wide-ranging implications for energy system transformations. With limited potential to capture and store emissions from combustion, the use of fossil fuels to provide final energy (particularly natural gas) is reduced substantially (Fig. 3e). There is greater reliance on electrification of end use sectors, as well as a more rapid scale up of green hydrogen and renewable heat, and greater long-term use of bioenergy. Bioenergy consumption increases in long-distance transport (aviation and shipping), as a limited supply of green H₂ is prioritised for industrial decarbonisation. Bioenergy also

substitutes for industrial fossil fuel consumption that would otherwise have been equipped with CCS. Renewables provide almost all the additional electricity generation required, with growth driven particularly by solar photovoltaics and offshore wind (Fig. 3f). Solar provides most of the additional generation pre-2050, while offshore wind emerges as a key source of low-carbon electricity in the latter half of the century. At the same time, the use of fossil gas in the power sector (with or without CCS) is reduced. Coal-fired generation is unchanged, as modelled 1.5°C scenarios all exhibit a global coal phaseout by 2030. BECCS deployment is also curtailed, as regions with high biomass potential do not necessarily have the CO₂ storage resources to develop a full CDR value chain. The potential for CCS to unlock ‘unburnable’ carbon (Budinis et al., 2017) is much lower, with the future use of fossil gas particularly impacted (Fig. 3g). Supplementary Fig. 1 displays final energy, electricity generation and fossil fuel consumption at the global level for each scenario separately.

3.2. Regional impacts of investable CO₂ storage constraints

We hypothesise that countries with well-appraised storage resources and the institutional/regulatory capacity to commercialise subsurface resources will be more able to build viable CCS enterprises than countries which lack such enabling factors. Therefore, regional distribution of CCS deployment will be highly heterogenous and may correlate with historical oil and gas extraction.

Fig. 4 displays CCS deployment in TIAM-Grantham for four illustrative regions: China, India, the Middle East and USA (see Supplementary Fig. 2 for detail on all regions). China and India have limited historical O&G extraction, but large potential demand for CCS due to growth of key emitting sectors such as energy intensive industry and power generation (IEA, 2021). While this demand for CO₂ storage can be met if storage is abundant (given by the technical potential), investment and regulatory constraints on CO₂ sequestration substantially reduce the level of CCS deployment. Low-carbon scenarios which assume abundant CO₂ storage resources may therefore significantly overestimate the potential for CCS deployment in these regions. For example, when the technical potential is used to represent CO₂ storage capacity, CCS deployment in China reaches almost 1GtCO₂/y by 2050 – over three times the maximum historic level of O&G extraction in the region. Building a CCS industry at this scale and pace is not impossible, but is likely to be fraught with uncertainty, highly challenging and costly, and

a path which China might choose to avoid or defer by embarking on alternative decarbonisation pathways which rely more heavily on renewables. The impact of limiting CO₂ sequestration to historical O&G extraction is even more marked when considering cumulative deployment.

Regions with storage capacity in excess of their domestic demands in 2050 include the Middle East and the USA. In modelled scenarios, these regions increase domestic CCS deployment to compensate for reduced carbon capture in other regions. Most of this CCS leakage involves CDR, with 75% of the increased sequestration in these regions due to greater domestic BECCS/DACCS deployment (Supplementary Fig. 3). The Middle East also uses more fossil gas with CCS to power high-temperature DACCS. In the Middle East, the availability of excess storage capacity across the time horizon allows cumulative CO₂ sequestration to double when regional storage capacities are limited to the investable potential. In the USA, while near-term sequestration can increase to compensate for lower capture elsewhere, in the long-term sequestration is reduced by the imposed limits on CO₂ storage, and hence cumulative deployment is approximately unchanged – although there is a switch to greater CDR deployment, at the expense of fossil CCS.

3.3. How to spend a dwindling CCS budget

If the potential for CO₂ storage is limited, then the question of prioritisation becomes central, as not all capture facilities will be able to access a scarce storage resource.

Scenarios which limit CO₂ storage via the investable potential have lower levels of overall CCS deployment (Fig. 5). Cumulative sequestration falls 50% from 850Gt to 422GtCO₂ when moving from technical to investable storage capacity estimates. Limited storage resources are then prioritised for carbon dioxide removal, with the use of fossil-CCS reduced substantially. With abundant CO₂ storage resources, fossil-CCS for use in electricity generation, hydrogen production and industry represents 43% of all CCS deployment, but this falls to 23% in scenarios with investment-based limits on CO₂ storage (Fig. 5). The role of CCS applied to fossil-based hydrogen production, already limited in 1.5°C scenarios, falls particularly sharply to almost zero.

To further explore the issue of prioritisation, Fig. 6 presents the sectoral deployment of CCS as a function of the global scale of storage availability. CO₂ injection rates range from 0-30GtCO₂/y, which is the maximum level of deployment observed in presented scenarios. TIAM-

Fig. 4. CO₂ sequestration rates for four illustrative regions, showing the impact of moving from technical estimates of CO₂ storage capacity potential (green) to estimates given by historical O&G extraction (red). Panels show (a): Change in sequestration in 2050 (b): Change in cumulative sequestration from 2020-2100

Fig. 5. Share of CCS by sector for 1.5°C scenarios with default technical CO₂ storage capacity (left) and the lower investable potential estimate linked to maximum historical O&G production (right).

Grantham prioritises very different applications depending on the availability of CO₂ storage. Three regions of CO₂ storage availability are identified.

In a regime of abundant CO₂ storage, injection rates in excess of 10GtCO₂/y are feasible. At 10GtCO₂/y, the majority (60%) of CCS deployment is via BECCS for use in power generation (BECCS-P). Industrial CCS is the next largest use-case, representing 17% of total sequestration. The deployment of BECCS in bioliqids production (BECCS-L) is very low, with transport predominantly decarbonised via electricity and green hydrogen. Further BECCS deployment is constrained by the availability of sustainable biomass, which is limited to 100-130EJ/y across the time horizon (see Section 2.3). As other CCS technologies are not limited by biomass availability (Supplementary Note 2), their deployment increases with CO₂ storage availability. Industrial CCS undergoes particularly strong growth, reflecting its wide set of potential applications. Cumulative sequestration from industrial CCS triples as feasible CO₂ injection rates grow from 10 to 30GtCO₂/y, and the share of sequestration represented by industrial CCS increases from 17 to 33% across this range.

In a regime of intermediate storage availability (4-5GtCO₂/y to 10GtCO₂/y), TIAM-Grantham begins to prioritise the use of BECCS-L. BECCS-P remains the largest CCS use-case, and while BECCS-P and DACCS deployment falls, their share of overall CCS deployment remains robust. BECCS-L predominantly takes market share from fossil CCS, particularly industry, as the largest application of fossil CCS in modelled scenarios.

Finally, in a regime of limited CO₂ storage availability where CO₂ injection rates are <4GtCO₂/y, scenarios prioritise BECCS-L, which accounts for up to 80% of cumulative CCS deployment in the most stringent scenarios. The use of BECCS in biofuel production over electricity generation represents a prioritisation of the energetic value of bioenergy (decarbonising challenging sectors) over the economic value (maximising negative emissions) (Klein et al., 2014; Köberle, 2019). This occurs because limited CCS deployment results in greater reliance on renewable energy vectors for end-use decarbonisation, as the potential to deploy fossil fuels with CCS is curtailed. This is particularly the case in the industrial sector, where electrolytic hydrogen displaces fossil-CCS to facilitate decarbonisation. This in turn reduces the availability of hydrogen for transport decarbonisation, particularly long-distance modes such as aviation and shipping. As a result, the value of biofuels in transport decarbonisation increases, and BECCS deployment in biofuel production is therefore prioritised.

Optimal CCS deployment depends heavily on the level of CO₂ storage available. In regimes with low availability, CCS deployment is driven

mainly by the need to provide energetic decarbonisation via biofuel production, while if large-scale CCS can be achieved, the predominant role for BECCS becomes CDR via power generation, and the role for bioliqids is very limited. Similarly, if CO₂ storage is a scarce good, then utilising it to store CO₂ from fossil fuels, particularly in industry, is a sub-optimal strategy, while in the event that CCS can be deployed at very large-scale, greater fossil-CCS can be incorporated into modelled pathways. This suggests there is a merit order for CCS, with different applications prioritised depending on the availability of CO₂ storage. Low-carbon scenarios produced by IAMs, if based on overoptimistic CO₂ storage potential estimates, may therefore provide misleading recommendations on the relative value of different CCS applications.

3.4. The potential role for trade in captured CO₂

Given the disparity between the location of capture facilities and investable storage resources, there could be a market for trade in captured CO₂ to match capture and storage facilities. Creating such a market would require multiple challenges to be overcome, including substantial new infrastructure investment in CO₂ transport and the development of a policy framework to regulate trade. We do not suggest such a market is a likely or an inevitable component of global climate action but present an exploratory scenario in which trade in CO₂ is enabled. It is also important to highlight that IAMs may overestimate the value of CCS and CDR in decarbonisation pathways for a variety of reasons (Grant et al., 2021a, 2021b, 2021c), and that actions which reduce the gross need for CCS, such as rapid electrification, efficiency and demand reduction (Barrett et al., 2022; Grubler et al., 2018; Luderer et al., 2021) could further reduce the perceived value of trade in captured CO₂ in modelled scenarios.

In TIAM-Grantham, the potential for interregional shipping of captured CO₂ leads to the development of a substantial global market through which 1.6GtCO₂/y is being traded by 2050, and by 2100 net cumulative trade in CO₂ has reached 121GtCO₂ (Fig. 7). China and India become large-scale exporters of captured CO₂ post-2050, increasing their capture rates beyond their sequestration rates. Regions with excess storage capacity such as the Middle East and the US reduce their capture rates to accommodate additional CO₂ from exporting regions.

In the early stages of the development of such a market, the majority of CO₂ is exported to excess capacity in Russia and the USA. However, in the long-term, the growth in domestic demand for CO₂ storage in these regions reduces their potential to take other regions' CO₂, and the Middle East emerges as the dominant sink region. Trade in captured CO₂ is predominantly used to optimise CDR deployment, particularly by

Fig. 6. (a) Displays the share of CCS by sector as a function of the global scale of CO₂ storage potential. (b) Displays cumulative sequestration of CO₂ by sector as a function of feasible CO₂ injection rates. Cumulative sequestration is calculated over the period 2020–2100.

Fig. 7. Interregional trade flows in captured CO₂ in 2050, and as cumulative flows across the time-horizon. Panels show (a/b) Capture/sequestration rates in illustrative regions in 2050, (c) Cross-border trade in captured CO₂ in 2050, (d/e) Cumulative capture/sequestration in illustrative regions, (f) Cumulative cross-border trade in captured CO₂

matching regional biomass potentials to regional storage potentials to enable greater BECCS deployment, with 80% of global trade used to facilitate CDR deployment (Fig. 8). Not all trade results in additional carbon dioxide removal, as in some cases imported CO₂ displaces domestic CDR—for example in the Middle East, DACCS deployment is reduced to accommodate CO₂ from other regions, thereby enabling

Fig. 8. Breakdown of CO₂ trade via commodity for a 1.5°C scenario with sequestration rates constrained by the investable CO₂ storage potential, and trade in captured CO₂ enabled. Note that cumulative trade here is slightly greater than in Fig. 6, as Fig. 6 calculates cumulative trade by region. Over the time-horizon, a given region can be an importer of one commodity but an exporter of another. For example, in scenarios applying the investable CO₂ storage potential and trade enabled, AFR imports industrial CO₂ pre-2050 when domestic demand for CCS is low, but is ultimately a net exporter of CO₂ from DAC plants (due to its relatively limited storage potential, but abundant renewable energy resources to drive DAC deployment). A region-based plot aggregates these contrasting flows and thus give a slightly lower trade-balance than a commodity-based plot).

greater BECCS deployment in storage-poor regions such as China and South America. Cumulative CDR deployment increases by 50GtCO₂ when trade is enabled.

While global CCS deployment is still limited to a maximum of 8.6GtCO₂/y, CO₂ trade enables faster utilisation of this storage resource (Fig. 9a). The global limit on CO₂ storage means that trade in CO₂ does not substantially alter the shape of the emissions pathway (Fig. 9b), with greater near-term emission reductions still required. However, the flexibility provided by a global market for captured CO₂ reduces abatement costs (Fig. 9c), with carbon prices falling 30% when inter-regional trade in captured CO₂ is allowed. The overall scale of mitigation investment required is slightly reduced marginally (Fig. 9d).

3.5. Sensitivity analyses

We explore how the key results presented in this analysis are dependent on the discount rate, the level of regional CO₂ injection rates, and the cost of trading captured CO₂.

3.5.1. Variations in the discount rate

The central analysis presented in this work uses a 5% discount rate – a value commonly used in mitigation analysis, but which has been criticised for being too high, leading to a structural disposition towards insufficient near-term action and overshoot-and-decline pathways (Emmerling et al., 2019). We repeat the analysis with 3% and 1% discount rates.

Scenarios with lower discount rates display greater near-term emission reductions and require less net-negative emissions in the latter half of the century to meet carbon budgets (Grant et al., 2021b). Low discount rate scenarios have higher near-term carbon prices, but these grow more slowly over the time horizon (Table 3).

As already seen in Section 3.1, limiting CO₂ injection to historical O&G extraction rates on a regional basis leads to higher policy costs. The higher policy cost largely arises from a shift in the emissions pathway towards one with greater near-term action and less reliance on net-negative emissions in the latter half of the century. Reducing the

Fig. 9. Displays results from 1.5°C scenarios where CO₂ sequestration is limited to historical O&G extraction, and trade in captured CO₂ is enabled or not. Panels show (a) Global CCS deployment, (b) CO₂ emissions, (c) carbon prices and (d) mitigation investments.

Table 3
Displays carbon prices for 1.5°C scenarios with 5%, 3% and 1% discount rates.

Scenario	2030 Carbon Price (\$/tCO ₂)	2050 Carbon Price (\$/tCO ₂)	2100 Carbon Price (\$/tCO ₂)
1.5°C / Technical Potential / 1% Discount Rate	370	460	750
1.5°C / Technical Potential / 3% Discount Rate	210	380	1650
1.5°C / Technical Potential / 5% Discount Rate	140	360	4160
1.5°C / Investable Potential / 1% Discount Rate	720	880	1440
1.5°C / Investable Potential / 3% Discount Rate	470	850	3720
1.5°C / Investable Potential / 5% Discount Rate	350	920	10,570

discount rate means that CO₂ injection rate constraints have a less substantial impact on the shape of the emissions pathway, as scenarios with low discount rates already display greater near-term emission reductions and reduced net-negative emissions (Supplementary Fig. 4). The influence of CO₂ injection rates constraints on the overall cost of

achieving 1.5°C is therefore reduced (Fig. 10). This suggests that, if policymakers place a high value on the welfare of future generations (as represented by a low discount rate), the impact of investment-based limits to CCS deployment will be less severe, emphasising again the importance of rapid decarbonisation in the 2020s to insure against the potential for limited CO₂ storage capacity.

3.5.2. Regional CO₂ injection rates and variations in the investable storage potential

The results of this analysis are driven by the use of regional O&G extraction rates to estimate the investable CO₂ storage potential. We explore how results differ if the investable potential is higher or lower than assumed in our central analysis. In doing so, we retain the following assumptions:

- For all storage reserves, injection rates will remain a central determinant of the CO₂ storage potential, and we therefore continue to limit CO₂ sequestration via injection rate constraints. Permeability remains a central concern across the time-horizon.
- Even if injection rates greater than historical O&G extraction can be achieved, storage deployment will remain somewhat correlated with O&G activity, as the ability to access subsurface resources of any type will still be easier for regions with expertise and regulatory experience in subsurface operations.

We explore two illustrative examples for variations in the investable

Fig. 10. Results of sensitivity analysis showing how global abatement costs increase when CO₂ injection rates are limited to historical O&G extraction. As the global discount rate is reduced, the impact of limited CCS deployment on system cost indicators falls. Panels show (a) Increase in carbon price and (b) Increase in total energy system costs.

potential for CO₂ storage. In the high investable potential case, then injection rates in 2050 are limited to historical O&G extraction, but post-2050, regions can exceed historical extraction, with injection rates able to grow a further 50% by 2100. In the low investable potential case, the roll-out of CCS is delayed, taking 50 years instead of 30 years to reach the scale of historical O&G extraction. This still represents a rapid growth to a scale that took the O&G sector one hundred years to establish.

If CO₂ storage potential is limited by injectivity considerations, rather than only gross volumetric capacity for storage, and if this storage potential has some degree of correlation with historical O&G extraction, then results are not particularly sensitive to the exact level of the investable potential (Fig. 11). Instead, results are driven by the regional heterogeneity which means that certain regions have abundant storage resources, while others have very limited CO₂ storage potential.

With a lower estimate of the investable potential for CO₂ storage, then CCS deployment is delayed, with only 4GtCO₂ being captured and stored by 2050 (Fig. 11a). However, the overall shape of the emissions pathway and the impact on system costs remains very similar to scenarios with a central estimate for investable potential (Fig. 11b–d). With a higher estimate of the investable potential, then CCS deployment reaches 13GtCO₂/y by 2100. However, the disparity between the location of accessible storage reserves and the location of capture facilities means that, even when the investable potential is increased, it does not necessarily lead to a corresponding increase in CCS deployment. CO₂ storage reserves must be in the right location to contribute to successful CCS deployment. As a result, deployment in 2100 is only up 20% at 10.3GtCO₂/y (Fig. 11a), and the decarbonisation pathway still displays greater near-term mitigation and higher policy costs than a pathway which assumes the technical potential for CO₂ storage can be accessed (Fig. 11b–d).

As the investable storage potential is varied, the relative deployment of CDR and fossil-CCS changes in a manner consistent with earlier findings on the prioritisation of CCS (Supplementary Fig. 5). While variations in the investable potential do not substantially affect results at

a global scale, they can have a significant impact on individual regions (Supplementary Fig. 6).

3.5.3. Cost of trading in captured CO₂

The central results in this paper suggest that a storage-constrained world would benefit from the emergence of a large-scale market in captured CO₂ to help match sources and sinks across the globe. We here assess how the scale and nature of this market depends on the cost of trading CO₂, by observing the changes in traded CO₂ volume over a range of shipping costs. The scale of the market for captured CO₂ is relatively robust to variations in the cost of shipping captured CO₂ (Fig. 11). In central scenarios, the cost of shipping CO₂ between regions is set at \$28/tCO₂, with 128GtCO₂ traded across the century. If the cost of shipping falls below \$10/tCO₂, then the scale of this market could increase to above 140GtCO₂ (Fig. 12). As the cost of shipping increases, the scale of the market for captured CO₂ falls, but only slightly. Even with a shipping cost of \$100/tCO₂ or more, 100Gt of captured CO₂ is traded over the time-period. This demonstrates the high value of CDR in modelled scenarios, with TIAM-Grantham utilising trade in CO₂ to expand the potential for negative emissions, even if this comes at a relatively high cost. Again, the value of CCS and CDR in TIAM-Grantham is likely an upper bound, which could be further reduced by greater representation of the potential for renewable-based electrification, lower discount rates, and alternative scenario design (Grant et al., 2021a, 2021b, 2021c). Representing these factors could reduce the value of CCS/CDR in TIAM-Grantham, and increase the sensitivity of CO₂ trade volumes to the cost of shipping.

4. Discussion and conclusions

In this study, we explore the role of CCS in achieving Paris Agreement goals in low-carbon scenarios produced by IAMs. Specifically, we focus on the implications for global and regional pathways if CO₂ storage is a limited and regionally heterogeneous resource, rather than the low-cost and globally abundant potential assumed by most IAMs. Given

Fig. 11. Results of sensitivity analysis displaying 1.5°C scenarios, where the CO₂ storage potential is varied between the technical potential and three different illustrative examples of the investable potential. Panels show (a) Global CCS deployment, (b) CO₂ emissions, (c) carbon prices and (d) mitigation investments.

Fig. 12. The global market for captured CO₂ as a function of the cost of interregional trade.

the influence of IAMs in shaping and informing the mitigation debate (Beck and Mahony, 2018), it is essential to explore the impact of critical uncertainties in these models and assess the implications for policy design.

Our results demonstrate that uncertainty around the feasible scale of CO₂ injection rates represents a critical, but neglected, factor in models producing low-carbon scenarios. Developing a global storage appraisal atlas to provide information on the investable potential for CO₂ storage by region would be a valuable tool to help calibrate CCS deployment rates in low-carbon scenarios to more realistic levels. By neglecting the key issue of achieving investable confidence in long-term injection rates (Lane et al., 2021), models which assume abundant and globally accessible CO₂ storage may substantially overestimate the role of CCS in low-carbon scenarios. We provide an initial *ad hoc* estimate of the investable CO₂ storage potential, using historical O&G extraction as a proxy for the conditions which could help enable largescale CO₂ storage. Large-scale CCS deployment is particularly challenging in regions which could have the greatest demand for CO₂ capture, such as China and India. If storage resources are indeed scarce and hard to develop, then the extent of necessary near-term decarbonisation increases, with significant consequences for the relative futures of renewable and fossil energy. This emphasises the importance of ratcheting near-term ambition to insure against possible deployment failure in CCS which cannot be disregarded.

Other analysis has considered the impact of limited CO₂ injection rates (Giannousakis et al., 2021), within a broader exploration of critical uncertainties in low-carbon scenarios. Our results agree with wider

analysis in the literature, highlighting that limited CO₂ injection rates require faster near-term decarbonisation driven by electrification, with higher marginal and gross policy costs. The results of Giannousakis et al. suggest that using peak-budget constraints can reduce reliance on CDR and limit the economic impact of constrained CO₂ sequestration in a manner similar to using lower discount rates in the analysis (Supplementary Note 3).

If CO₂ storage potential is limited, then the question of prioritisation becomes central. Not all capture facilities will be able to access a scarce CO₂ storage resource, and our results suggest that certain CCS technologies should take priority over others, following a merit order linked to the contribution to decarbonisation of hard-to-abate sectors. In TIAM-Grantham, BECCS-L deployment is at the front of the merit order and is prioritised in the case of very limited CO₂ storage potential as it enables decarbonisation of shipping and aviation, which have few alternative options to reduce emissions in modelled scenarios. More broadly, carbon dioxide removal technologies take precedence over fossil-CCS in the case of limited CO₂ storage capacity. While there are abundant opportunities for CCS in industrial decarbonisation, this research suggests that industrial CCS is further down the merit order. This suggests that the large-scale use of CCS in industry (i.e., beyond least-regrets CCS deployment to capture non-combustion emissions from cement and other processes) is dependent on overcoming limits to CO₂ storage potential, an uncertain prospect. Identifying alternative decarbonisation options for industry that reduce CCS reliance is therefore essential (Madeddu et al., 2020). There is a significant mismatch between the prioritisation of CCS projects suggested by this research and the current suite of demonstration and deployment projects (GCCSI, 2020). Current demonstration projects include large numbers of fossil CCS plants (GCCSI, 2021) which therefore risk utilising a scant CCS resource in a non-optimal manner. While pilot projects could theoretically provide useful learning for developing a global CCS industry, we should be cautious about extensive deployment of low-merit-order CCS technologies and plan this carefully so as to not rule out space for the most essential CCS projects in the future, should CO₂ storage transpire to be a scarce resource. Rapid emission reductions in the next decade emerge as a viable strategy to hedge against the risk of low CCS availability by mid-century (Grant et al., 2021a).

Constraints on CO₂ storage capacity could to some extent be circumvented by greater carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) in a wide range of applications including production of synthetic fuels, chemical manufacture, or longer-lived products such as construction materials (Baena-Moreno et al., 2019). Some CCU options however would not lead to permanent CO₂ storage, as CO₂ is released when the chemical is used or the fuel is burned (Mac Dowell et al., 2017). The use of atmospheric CO₂ captured by DAC could close this loop (Graves et al., 2011), but CCU still faces challenges relating to energetic cost of producing products with CO₂ (Mac Dowell et al., 2017) and competition with alternative means of end-use decarbonisation, such as hydrogen and biomass (Davis et al., 2018). Semi-permanent CO₂ storage through concrete curing or mixing could expand the storage potential by 0.1-1.4GtCO₂/y by 2050 (Hepburn et al., 2019). However, the climate benefit of such approaches has been challenged literature (Ravikumar et al., 2021), and thus their potential remains uncertain. While some have suggested that CCU represents a minimal contribution to the mitigation challenge (Mac Dowell et al., 2017), scenarios with CCU for synthetic fuel production are now entering the literature (Rodrigues et al., 2021). Future work could explore how including CCU would affect the results of analysis. Including CCU would reduce the impact of limiting the CO₂ storage potential, but for the reasons outlined above, the overall impact would likely remain relatively small.

Our results suggest that enabling trade in captured CO₂ could reduce the impact of regional CO₂ storage capacity constraints. Interregional trade in captured CO₂ represents a speculative but possible option to help achieve large-scale deployment of CCS. Our analysis of a global market in captured CO₂ is exploratory in nature but suggests that there

could be clear winners and losers in such a market. Regions with well-characterised storage resources in excess of domestic demand, most notably the Middle East but also the US, EU and Russia, could benefit from a global market, selling CO₂ storage to other regions. China, India, South America and others could be buyers on this market, as they may struggle to appraise and develop large-scale domestic CO₂ storage. Creating a global market for captured CO₂ would require large-scale new infrastructure, developing a trade framework, and most importantly, a carbon market. Central questions that would need to be addressed include:

- How would a market for captured CO₂ interact with Article 6 of the Paris Agreement? In particular, if CDR value chains are international, with capture and storage occurring in different jurisdictions, who is able to claim the sequestered emissions in their territorial accounts?
- How might trade costs in this market be distributed in a manner which is consistent with concepts of equity, particularly common but differentiated responsibilities? For example, would it be equitable for the USA to charge for access to its storage resources? Or could access to storage resources form a new form of international cooperation and capacity building, alongside climate finance and technology transfer?

Achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement will be a highly challenging endeavour, requiring rapid and unprecedented transformation of the global energy system. This research does not intend to argue that CCS has no value in limiting global warming, but rather to critique and improve the representation of CCS in low-carbon scenarios produced by IAMs. More realistic representation of regional CO₂ storage potentials in IAMs can help ensure that decision-making is robust to potential limits to CCS deployment, that CO₂ storage resources are utilised in an optimal manner, and that critical challenges to deploying CCS at scale are highlighted and addressed. Ultimately, this can help maximise CCS's constructive contribution to the decarbonisation challenge, and with it, our chances at preventing dangerous climate change.

Data availability

Supporting data for this analysis is available from the authors upon request.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Neil Grant: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ajay Gambhir:** Writing – review & editing. **Shivika Mittal:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Chris Greig:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Alexandre C. Köberle:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

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